

Projection of Long-Term Agricultural Energy Demand in Ethiopia

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Executive Summary

This study presents a comprehensive projection of long-term agricultural energy demand in Ethiopia from 2022 to 2050 using the MAED (Model for Analysis of Energy Demand) framework. It evaluates four scenarios: business as usual (BAU), high gross domestic product (GDP) growth, sector-specific plan and energy efficiency and fuel switch. Results indicate a significant increase in energy demand across all scenarios, with the BAU scenario increasing from about 7.28 PJ in 2022 to over 36.2 PJ (401%) by 2050 and the high GDP scenario peaking at 71.3 PJ (879%) by 2050. The sector-specific policy plan results in demand reaching 25.1 PJ (244%) by 2050, driven by targeted agricultural policies and rural development efforts. Traditional fuels remain dominant, particularly in the high GDP and sector-specific policy cases. However, the energy efficiency and fuel switch scenario demonstrates a more sustainable trajectory, with slower energy demand growth 16.1 PJ (132%) by 2050 and reduced dependency on traditional fuels through improved efficiency and cleaner alternatives such as solar thermal and modern biomass.

Key lessons highlight the urgent need to decouple economic growth from traditional fuel reliance in agriculture. Actionable recommendations include: developing and implementing clean energy policies tailored to the agricultural sector, promoting the adoption of energy-efficient technologies in the agricultural sector, accelerate fuel-switching from traditional biomass to modern and renewable energy sources through targeted subsidies, and enhancing rural electrification using decentralized renewable energy systems. In addition, policymakers should integrate energy planning with national agricultural and climate strategies to ensure resilient, low-carbon, and inclusive rural development. Further, investment in research is required to assess cost effectiveness of implementation pathways for clean energy transitions.

Key words: Agricultural Energy Demand, Energy Forecasting, MAED Model, Traditional Fuels, Renewable Energy , Energy Efficiency

1. Introduction

The agricultural sector remains the cornerstone of Ethiopia's economy, contributing 30.8% of the national GDP in the base year 2022, when the country's GDP was USD 126.78 billion (*IMF, International Monetary Fund report 2024*). Understanding and forecasting energy demand in this sector is critical for supporting sustainable economic growth and effective energy planning. This study employs MAED to project long-term agricultural energy requirements up to 2050 under various socio-economic and policy-driven scenarios. The analysis considers BAU, high GDP growth, sector-specific policy interventions, and an energy efficiency and fuel switching scenario. These pathways reflect differing assumptions on GDP growth, energy consumption patterns, and technological shifts, offering valuable insights for policy-makers to formulate sustainable energy strategies tailored to Ethiopia's evolving agricultural landscape.

Purpose

- ✓ To estimate the long-term energy demand of Ethiopia's agricultural sector under various development scenarios using MAED.

Scope

- ✓ The study focuses exclusively on Ethiopia's agricultural sector, covering thermal, motive, and electricity energy uses from 2022 to 2050, based on national GDP projections and sectoral assumptions.

Objectives and Aims

- ✓ To apply the MAED model to forecast agricultural energy demand up to 2050.
- ✓ To analyze the impact of economic growth, sectoral policies, and fuel transition strategies on agricultural sector final energy demand.
- ✓ To support evidence-based planning for energy infrastructure and sustainability in agriculture.

2. Methodology

This study adopts a bottom-up modelling approach using MAED, a widely used tool developed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) to project long-term energy demand based on socioeconomic drivers and sectoral activity indicators. MAED allows disaggregation of energy use by sector, end-use, and energy form, making it particularly suitable for analyzing agricultural energy demand under diverse scenarios.

The analysis uses 2022 as the base year and extends projections to 2050, based on the availability of complete input data required by the MAED model. A key macroeconomic input is Ethiopia's GDP in 2022, which stood at USD 126.78 billion, with the agricultural sector accounting for 30.8% of this total (*IMF, International Monetary Fund report 2024*). Historical and sector-specific final energy demand data were obtained from sources (*WB, world bank report, 2022*), (*Ethiopian Central Statistics Agency (CSA) report, 2022*), and (*IEA, "International energy Agency, 2022*). These data informed the development of MAED input parameters, particularly for agricultural activities and energy intensities.

Four scenarios were developed. These are:

- **BAU:** projects the energy demand and consumption patterns based on current trends without any new changes in energy policies and technologies.
- **High GDP:** the expansion of industrial park and completion of Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) may increase the GDP of the country, and based on these economic driving constraints this scenario was created.
- **Sector-specific policy plan:** the federal democratic republic of Ethiopia planning and development commission plan was taken as direction to reduce the share of the agriculture sector from the total share (*Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia, "planning and development commission plan report" 2021*).
- **Energy efficiency and fuel switch:** this scenario was created based on the Climate-Resilient Green Economy (CRGE) Strategy of Ethiopia (*UN Climate Change working report, 2021*).

The details about the scenario's key assumption and descriptions considered in the model are shown in Table 2.1

Table 2.1 scenarios key assumption and descriptions.

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Business as Usual (BAU)	GDP growth rate (6.4%) and agricultural share of GDP (30.8) remain constant throughout the projection period (2022–2050)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ End-user energy consumption breakdown: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Thermal use: 85% ✓ Motive power: 10% ✓ Electricity use: 5%
High GDP	High GDP growth with agricultural shares 30.8% held constant at BAU levels.	❖ A 9% GDP growth rate is assumed.
Sector-Specific Policy Plan	2.5% GDP growth rate over the projection period (2022-2050) and the agricultural sector's GDP share is deduced.	❖ The sectoral share is reduced by 7% over the model period
Energy efficiency and Fuel switch	The agricultural sector's GDP share (reduced by 7% over the model ,period) fuel switching, and energy efficiency are adjusted	❖ Energy efficiency improved by 7%, while traditional fuel use fell by 25% and fossil fuel penetration declined by 3.5%. Meanwhile, modern biomass rose by 25% and solar thermal increased by 3.5% over the model period

3. Results

Based on the outlined methodology, the following results were obtained.

3.1 Business as Usual (BAU)

Figure 3.1 shows a steady rise in Ethiopia's agricultural energy demand under the BAU scenario, increasing from about 7.28 PJ in 2022 to over 36.2 PJ (401%) by 2050. Traditional fuels dominate, growing sharply and remaining the primary energy source. Modern biomass, electricity, solar thermal, fossil fuels, and motor fuels show only modest increases.

Figure 3.1: Projected total energy demand under the BAU Scenario

3.2 High GDP

Figure 3.2 shows a sharp rise in agricultural energy demand under the high GDP scenario, growing from around 7.28 PJ in 2022 to nearly 71.3 PJ (879%) by 2050. Traditional fuels remain the dominant source, increasing significantly, while modern biomass, electricity, fossil fuels, and motor fuels show moderate growth. The surge reflects strong economic expansion, driving higher energy needs without a major shift in the fuel mix. This highlights the importance of integrating clean energy policies with economic growth to avoid deepening reliance on traditional fuels.

Figure 3.2: Projected total energy demand under the high GDP growth scenario

3.3 Sector-Specific Policy Plan

Figure 3.3 shows a gradual increase in agricultural energy demand under the sector-specific policy plan scenario, rising from approximately 7.28 PJ in 2022 to about 25.1 PJ (244%) by 2050. Traditional fuels continue to dominate the energy mix, with a notable increase over time, while modern biomass, electricity, fossil fuels, and motor fuels experience moderate growth. Although cleaner sources are gradually being adopted, the heavy reliance on traditional fuels indicates a slow transition. This outcome reflects the challenges in rapidly transforming the energy structure of Ethiopia's agriculture, despite policy efforts. However, it also aligns with the national development strategy, which envisions a gradual reduction in agriculture's share of GDP through structural economic transformation, aiming to shift toward a more industrial and service-oriented economy. As agricultural energy demand stabilizes relative to other sectors, there is an opportunity to focus policy efforts on cleaner energy adoption within agriculture, improving sustainability without hindering productivity.

Figure 3.3: Projected energy demand under the sector-specific policy plan scenario

3.4 Energy efficiency and Fuel switch

Figure 3.4 illustrates a modest increase in agricultural energy demand under the energy efficiency and fuel switch scenario, rising from approximately 7.28 PJ in 2022 to around 16.1 PJ (132%) by 2050. While traditional fuels still contribute significantly, their share steadily declines compared to the sector-specific policy scenario. This shift is driven by improvements in energy efficiency and a gradual transition from traditional and fossil fuels to cleaner sources like modern biomass and solar thermal energy. The trend aligns with Ethiopia's national policies promoting sustainable energy use, such as the Climate Resilient Green Economy (CRGE) Strategy and the National Electrification Program (NEP), which encourage cleaner technologies in agriculture. This scenario underscores the critical role of targeted policy interventions in fostering energy transition while supporting economic growth and environmental sustainability in the agricultural sector.

Figure 3.4: Projected energy demand under the energy efficiency and fuel switching scenario

5. Discussion

This study provides long-term projections of energy demand in Ethiopia's agricultural sector using the MAED, under four different scenarios: BAU, high GDP growth, sector-specific plan and energy efficiency and fuel switch. Insights derived from these scenarios offer important implications for policy design, technology planning, and sustainable energy transition strategies in Ethiopia's agricultural sector, which currently accounts for approximately 30.8% of GDP.

Under the BAU scenario, total final energy demand is projected to increase significantly from 7.28 PJ in 2022 to over 36.2 PJ by 2050. Traditional fuels mainly firewood and crop residues remain dominant, reflecting the sector's continued dependence on biomass. This trajectory indicates a slow pace of modernization and limited transition to cleaner energy sources. If no major interventions are made, this dependence may lead to resource depletion, environmental degradation, and inefficient energy use.

In contrast, the high GDP growth scenario predicts a sharper increase in energy demand, reaching about 71.3 PJ by 2050. This spike results from increased mechanization, irrigation expansion, and intensified agricultural production. While modern energy sources such as electricity, fossil fuels, and modern biomass show some growth, traditional fuels still dominate the energy mix. This scenario underscores the trade-off between economic growth and sustainable energy use, especially if clean energy integration is not prioritized.

The energy efficiency and fuel switch scenario, however, presents a more sustainable outlook. Here, energy demand grows only moderately from 7.2 PJ to 16.1 PJ by 2050 despite economic development. The share of traditional fuels declines due to increased efficiency and a shift toward solar thermal and modern biomass. This result highlights the transformative potential of clean energy technologies and targeted energy policies. Compared to the sector-specific policy scenario, where traditional fuel use continues to rise significantly, energy efficiency and fuel switch scenario represents a promising path that balances economic growth, sustainability, and energy efficiency.

Key Recommendations are:

Policy support is essential. The government should strengthen enforcement of Ethiopia's Climate-Resilient Green Economy (CRGE) strategy and align agricultural energy use with the country's updated National Electrification Program (NEP 2.0), which emphasizes productive uses of electricity. Financial incentives for renewable technologies, capacity building for rural farmers, and public-private partnerships can further accelerate clean energy adoption.

While the MAED model offers a robust framework for projecting long-term energy demand, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the model assumes a linear relationship between

GDP growth and energy demand, which may not fully capture socio-economic or technological shifts over time. Second, data on disaggregated energy use in agriculture especially for off-grid and informal energy sources is limited in Ethiopia, which may affect model accuracy. Moreover, the modeling does not incorporate extreme weather events or climate variability, which can significantly affect agricultural productivity and energy use.

7. Conclusion

This study assessed long-term energy demand in Ethiopia's agricultural sector under four scenarios: BAU, high GDP growth, sector-specific plan and energy efficiency and fuel switch, using the MAED model. The findings show that without targeted interventions, energy demand will increase sharply, with traditional fuels remaining dominant, especially under the high GDP growth and sector-specific policy scenarios. However, the energy efficiency and fuel switch scenario demonstrates a more sustainable path, where energy demand rises modestly and the reliance on traditional fuels decreases through cleaner technologies and efficiency gains. A key lesson is that economic growth alone does not guarantee sustainable energy use strategic policies and clean energy integration are essential.

Based on the analysis, it is recommended that Ethiopia prioritize the deployment of solar thermal, modern biomass, and energy-efficient technologies in the agricultural sector. Strengthening policies such as the Climate-Resilient Green Economy strategy and National Electrification Program, alongside investment in decentralized renewable energy solutions, is critical. Additionally, capacity building, financial incentives, and improved data collection will support effective policy implementation and future research. Aligning agricultural modernization with clean energy goals is vital for ensuring food security, energy access, and environmental sustainability.

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